

newly identified CR lines was unknown, so we continued to observe their performance in the advanced generations and to compare them with their parents. The CR lines had 40 to 93% fewer cracked grains and 25 to 85% less shelling breakage than their parents. Seasonal effects caused

more variation in parent than CR lines. Halubbalu had exceptional resistance to cracking and breakage and high genetic stability.

In each variety and derivative, the percentage of cracked grains varied with the percentage of shelling breakage and served

as a round index for predicting breakage properties (see figure).

Future genetic study of crack resistance should elucidate the chemical nature of the endosperm in relation to cracking. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DISEASE RESISTANCE

Recovery from blast (B1) defoliation in rice

*A. J. Carpenter, and A. I. Khatibu,
Kilimo/FAO, Box 159, Zanzibar, Tanzania*

During screening of rice lines for B1 resistance, we recorded disease at 5 and 8 wk after seeding. The lines were F₆ selections bred for earliness and resistance to late season drought under rainfed conditions. At 8 wk several B1-susceptible lines had produced vigorous new growth following B1 attack scored at 6-8 by the 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Other B1-susceptible lines under the same management had little or no recovery. Many of the recovered lines yielded 3-4 t/ha. The selection procedure employed in F₄ and F₅ for those lines involved digging up surviving plants from a drought-affected, largely dead segregating population, and encouraging, under irrigation, new growth from ratoon tillers to produce seed.

If confirmed, the existence of strong genetically controlled differences in recovery between varieties following defoliation should be of interest to rice breeders. Apart from drought and B1, insects such as caseworms, leafhoppers, and grasshoppers frequently reduce crop leaf area. Some recovery from hopperburn could also be envisaged.

B1 recovery also could be included in a disease resistance breeding program. If race changes of the B1 fungus cause susceptibility, a variety with both vertical resistance and residual recovery ability should give farmers and breeders time to identify a replacement variety. Testing for recovery in a vertically resistant varie-

Table 1. Lines with best recovery, Zanzibar, Tanzania.

Cross	Line no.
BKN/IRAT	746c, 345, 3029A & B, 333
BKN/1746	777B, 770A, 2031
3839/DV	715A
IAC/Bb	172c, 179CB, 200A
Aus/Bin	501A, 3000
IRAT/Bg	177c, 177f, 3021c
Bb/Affa	703a

ty poses some problems. Mowing or a sublethal paraquat spray might be effective, but we have not tested those methods.

Screening for brown spot (BS) resistance in deep water rice

*Y. Prasad and R. S. Singh, Rajendra
Agricultural University, Pusa, Bihar,
India 848125*

BS, caused by *Drechslera oryzae*, is a major disease of long-duration, lowland, deep water, and floating rices. In 1982, three deep water screening sets (IRDWON I, II, and III) with 156 lines, received through the International Rice Testing Program, were grown in deep water areas at Pusa and evaluated for BS resistance. The varieties and lines were sown directly in the fields and spray-inoculated with *Drechslera oryzae* suspension in Sep. Flowering rices were scored for resistance using the 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice* in Oct.

Five alternate leaves beginning with the flag leaf were scored and the highest score was considered an index of the entry. Local severity index was 7.2 in 1982 and 7.9 in 1983. Resistant lines

Table 2. Parents and origin of lines with best recovery, Zanzibar, Tanzania.

Parent	Source (via IRTP)
BKN6858-6-3-2	Thailand
IRAT 10	Ivory Coast
IAC25	Brazil
IR1746-226	IRRI
IR3839	IRRI
Aus 8	India
Affa Kilombero	Tanzania
BG33-2	Sri Lanka
DV110	Bangladesh

Table 1 lists the lines with the best recovery, and Table 2 gives their parentage. □

Reaction of deep water rice cultures to BS in 1982 and 1983, Bihar, India.

Designation	Resistance level ^a		Reaction
	1982	1983	
CR98-7216-CRRP-34	3	3	R
CR149-5010-228	3	7	S
IR4829-89-2	3	7	S
CR1002	3	3	R
IR3257-24-IB-P 2	3	7	S
IR19061-57-IE-PI	3	7	S
Achra 108-1	3	5	MR
BKNFR2606-3-2-1-2	3	3	R
IR42	3	4	R
BKNFR76004-4-1-1-1	3	5	MR
BKNFR76052-100-1-5-1	4	7	S
BKNFR76025-100-1-5-2	4	7	S
Bajal (check)	7	9	S

^aBy the 1980 SES.

identified in 1982 also were evaluated in 1983. Local Bajal was the check. Of the 12 test lines selected, CR98-7216-CRRP-34, CR1002, BKNFR2606-3-2-1-2, and IR42 had consistent resistant reactions (see table). □